

SPATIAL INTERPOLATION IN R: THE RFSI METHOD

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ABSTRACT

Spatial interpolation is a fundamental task in geospatial analysis, enabling the estimation of variable values at unsampled locations based on observations collected at discrete spatial points. A wide range of methods has been developed for this purpose, including deterministic approaches, geostatistical techniques, regression-based models, and modern machine learning algorithms. While classical methods such as inverse distance weighting and Kriging have been widely used due to their interpretability and theoretical foundation, they often rely on strong assumptions or require extensive parameter tuning. In contrast, machine learning methods provide high predictive flexibility but typically lack explicit mechanisms to incorporate spatial autocorrelation. This paper presents an overview of spatial interpolation methods implemented in the R programming environment, with a particular focus on the Random Forest Spatial Interpolation (RFSI) approach. RFSI integrates spatial context directly into a machine learning framework by incorporating information from neighboring observations as predictive features, thereby combining the strengths of Random Forest models with spatial dependency structures. The method reduces reliance on explicit variogram modelling while effectively capturing nonlinear spatial relationships. The paper summarizes key interpolation methodologies, discusses their implementation in R, and introduces the RFSI method and its associated R package `meteo`. The results highlight the potential of spatial machine learning approaches as flexible and efficient alternatives for spatial prediction tasks across a variety of application domains.

Keywords: spatial interpolation, machine learning, Random Forest, RFSI, R, `meteo`.

1 Introduction

Spatial data consist of observations located in space together with associated attributes. These attributes may represent measured, observed, or modeled properties of natural or human-related phenomena and can be quantitative, qualitative, or categorical. Spatial data are commonly represented as vector data, describing discrete entities through points, lines, and polygons, or as raster data, where space is divided into regular grid cells containing attribute values. Due to the increasing availability of remote sensing products, sensor networks, and geographic information systems, spatial data have become essential in numerous scientific and applied disciplines, including environmental sciences, hydrology, agriculture, urban planning, transportation, and related fields.

In many real-world applications, observations are available only at a limited number of sampled locations, while the objective is to estimate variable values continuously across the entire spatial domain. Spatial interpolation methods estimate values at unsampled locations using observations

from nearby locations and their spatial relationships. The underlying assumption of most interpolation approaches is that nearby observations are more similar than distant ones, a principle commonly formalized as Tobler's First Law of Geography. Spatial interpolation is widely applied in the production of continuous maps of environmental, socio-economic, and infrastructural variables and represents one of the fundamental tasks in spatial analysis and geostatistics.

Numerous interpolation methods have been developed over the last decades, ranging from deterministic approaches to geostatistical methods and modern machine learning (ML) algorithms. Although geostatistical methods often provide high prediction accuracy, they rely on assumptions regarding stationarity and spatial covariance structures, which may not hold for complex real-world phenomena [1]. On the other hand, ML algorithms are capable of modelling nonlinear relationships but are not inherently spatial and often fail to explicitly account for spatial autocorrelation. Existing approaches that incorporate spatial information into ML models commonly rely on spatial coordinates, residual kriging, or engineered distance-based covariates (i.e., auxiliary spatial predictors defined over the interpolation domain), each of which has certain limitations related to model complexity, computational efficiency, or prediction artifacts.

The Random Forest Spatial Interpolation (RFSI) [2] method was developed to address these limitations by integrating spatial context directly into an ML framework. RFSI incorporates spatial dependence by using values of nearest observations and their distances as additional predictors in a Random Forest (RF) model [3], allowing the model to account for spatial autocorrelation without explicit variogram modelling. In this way, RFSI combines the flexibility and nonlinear modelling capabilities of ML methods with the fundamental spatial principle that nearby observations are more related than distant ones. It has been demonstrated that RFSI can achieve competitive or superior prediction accuracy compared to traditional geostatistical and ML interpolation approaches while maintaining straightforward implementation and computational efficiency.

The objective of this paper is to provide a concise overview of spatial interpolation methods available in the R programming environment, with a particular focus on the RFSI method and its implementation. The paper briefly reviews the main groups of interpolation approaches, discusses the methodological background of RFSI, and presents its implementation through the R package `meteo`. Additionally, the paper highlights the main advantages, limitations, and potential future developments of the RFSI approach for spatial prediction tasks.

2 Spatial interpolation methods

Spatial interpolation represents the process of estimating values of a variable at unobserved locations based on observations collected at known locations. The main assumption behind most interpolation approaches is spatial autocorrelation, i.e., the tendency of nearby observations to be more similar than distant ones. Interpolation methods are widely used for producing continuous spatial surfaces and maps in numerous scientific and applied fields, including environmental sciences, hydrology, agriculture, urban planning, transportation, climatology, among others.

Spatial interpolation methods can generally be divided into deterministic, geostatistical, regression-based, ML, and hybrid approaches. Deterministic methods estimate values directly from neighboring observations using mathematical functions or distance-based weighting schemes. Common examples include nearest neighbor interpolation (NN), inverse distance weighting (IDW), trend surface mapping (TS), local trend surfaces, spline interpolation, thin plate splines (TPS), triangulated irregular networks (TIN), and local polynomial interpolation [4]. These methods are

straightforward, computationally efficient, and easy to implement, but they often fail to adequately model complex spatial variability and typically do not provide uncertainty estimates.

Geostatistical methods explicitly model spatial dependence through covariance or variogram functions. The most widely used geostatistical approach is Kriging [5], which includes several variants such as ordinary kriging, simple kriging, universal kriging, co-kriging, indicator kriging, and sequential simulations [4]. These methods provide statistically optimal predictions under specific assumptions regarding spatial stationarity and covariance structure and are capable of generating prediction uncertainty estimates. However, geostatistical approaches may require substantial expertise for variogram modelling and can become computationally demanding for large datasets.

Regression-based interpolation methods combine observed data with auxiliary predictors (covariates) describing environmental or spatial conditions. Multiple linear regression (MLR), geographically weighted regression (GWR) [6], generalized additive models (GAM) [7], and TS models are frequently used examples. These approaches are particularly effective when strong relationships exist between the target variable and environmental covariates such as elevation, land cover, or remotely sensed variables. Nevertheless, regression models may have difficulties capturing complex nonlinear relationships and residual spatial dependence.

ML methods are increasingly used for spatial prediction due to their ability to model nonlinear relationships and interactions among predictors. Commonly used methods include RF [3], Support Vector Machines (SVM) [8], Artificial Neural Networks (ANN) [7], Gradient Boosting Machines (GBM) [9], and Cubist models. Although these approaches often achieve high predictive accuracy, they are not inherently spatial and therefore usually rely only on covariates without explicitly accounting for spatial autocorrelation.

Hybrid interpolation approaches combine multiple interpolation paradigms in order to exploit their complementary strengths. Common examples include residual IDW, residual kriging (mostly regression kriging) [10], where deterministic or geostatistical interpolation is applied to model residual spatial variability remaining after regression or ML prediction.

Spatial ML methods extend traditional ML approaches by incorporating spatial context directly into the modelling process. Spatial information can be introduced through coordinates, neighborhood statistics, distances to nearby observations, spatial residuals, or other spatial predictors [11]. Methods such as Random Forest Spatial Interpolation (RFSI) belong to this group and combine the nonlinear modelling capabilities of ML with spatial dependence information traditionally modeled using geostatistical approaches. An overview of commonly used spatial interpolation methods is given in Table 1.

Modern spatial interpolation workflows in R are commonly supported by packages for spatial data manipulation such as the R packages `sf` [12] and `terra` [13], which provide efficient handling of vector and raster spatial data and interoperability with interpolation and ML libraries. A comprehensive overview of R packages for spatial data handling, analysis, visualization, and modelling is available through the official CRAN Spatial Task View: Analysis of Spatial Data [14], which serves as the primary reference for the R spatial ecosystem.

Table 1 Overview of commonly used spatial interpolation methods and corresponding R packages.

Method group	Methods	Input data	Main characteristics	R packages
Deterministic methods	NN, IDW, TS, local trend surfaces, spline, TPS, TIN, local polynomial	Observed values only	Simple and computationally efficient; does not provide uncertainty estimation	<code>gstat</code> , <code>fields</code> , <code>terra</code> , <code>spatial</code>
Geostatistical methods	Kriging (ordinary, simple, universal (with coordinates as predictors), co-kriging, indicator, simulations)	Observed values only	Variogram-based, uncertainty estimation, statistically optimal predictions	<code>gstat</code> , <code>automap</code> , <code>geOR</code> , <code>spBayes</code>
Regression methods	MLR, GWR, GAM	Environmental covariates only	Uses auxiliary predictors and environmental relationships	<code>stats</code> , <code>spgwr</code> , <code>mgcv</code>
ML methods	RF, SVM, ANN, GBM, Cubist	Environmental covariates only	Flexible nonlinear modelling without explicit spatial context	<code>randomForest</code> , <code>ranger</code> , <code>caret</code> , <code>e1071</code> , <code>gbm</code> , <code>Cubist</code>
Hybrid methods	Residual IDW, residual kriging, regression kriging	Observed values and covariates	Combines regression/ML with residual spatial interpolation	<code>gstat</code> , <code>meteo</code>
Spatial ML methods	RFSI, RFsp, spatial RF approaches	Observed values and covariates	ML with direct incorporation of spatial context	<code>meteo</code> , <code>GSIF</code> , <code>CAST</code>

3 RFSI method

Classical spatial interpolation methods such as Kriging, IDW, and other deterministic approaches rely explicitly on spatial autocorrelation and distance-decay assumptions. In contrast, modern ML methods such as RF typically ignore spatial autocorrelation directly and instead rely on environmental covariates (e.g., elevation, satellite products, coordinates). While this often works well, it neglects a key principle of spatial statistics: nearby observations contain the strongest information about an unknown location.

To address this limitation, Random Forest Spatial Interpolation (RFSI) [2] explicitly incorporates spatial dependence in a natural way by including observations at nearest locations and their distances as predictors. This bridges the gap between geostatistical thinking (kriging-like neighborhood dependence) and flexible nonlinear ML models.

3.1 Methodology

RFSI extends standard RF [3] by explicitly embedding local spatial dependence into the feature space. Instead of relying only on environmental covariates at the prediction location, RFSI augments the model with information from nearby observations. For each location s_0 , the method identifies the n nearest sampled locations $s_i (i=1, \dots, n)$. From these neighbors, two types of spatial predictors are constructed: (1) the observed target values $z(s_i)$, and (2) the corresponding Euclidean distances $d_i = |s_i - s_0|$. The final predictive model can be expressed as:

$$\hat{z}(s_0) = f(x_1(s_0), \dots, x_m(s_0), z(s_1), d_1, z(s_2), d_2, z(s_3), d_3, \dots, z(s_n), d_n)$$

where $x_i(s_0) (i=1, \dots, m)$ represents m optional environmental covariates and f is an RF regression model.

The workflow consists of four main steps (Fig. 1). First, the n nearest locations are identified for every training location. Second, a structured learning dataset (regression matrix) is created by appending neighbor values and distances to the other environmental covariates. Third, an RF model is trained on this enriched feature set. Finally, predictions are made by repeating the same neighbor extraction process for unseen locations and applying the trained model.

Figure 1 RFSI method workflow [2].

3.2 Results summary

RFSI offers a combination of geostatistical intuition and ML flexibility. A key advantage is that it removes the need for variogram modelling and the associated assumptions of stationarity and distributional form required in classical Kriging. This makes the method easier to apply in practice, particularly for complex or highly skewed variables where variogram fitting is unstable or

ambiguous. At the same time, RFSI is able to model nonlinear relationships between predictors and the target variable, unlike Kriging or regression-based approaches. This is particularly effective when spatial patterns are driven by multiple interacting environmental processes. Another advantage is robustness across data types. The method performs well for zero-inflated and highly skewed variables such as daily precipitation, where many traditional geostatistical approaches struggle. From an implementation perspective, RFSI is straightforward: it requires only nearest neighbor search and a standard RF model. It also scales better than buffer-based RF extensions such as RFsp [1], since it avoids constructing large distance rasters for every observation. Finally, RFSI provides interpretable spatial structure through feature importance of neighbor ranks, allowing direct assessment of how much information is contributed by the closest observations compared to more distant ones and compared to environmental covariates.

Across all experiments, RFSI demonstrated consistently strong predictive performance, evaluated against deterministic interpolation methods, Kriging variants, standard RF, and RFsp. In the synthetic experiments based on simulated stationary Gaussian fields, ordinary kriging (OK) remained the optimal method, as expected from its theoretical properties. However, RFSI achieved performance close to ordinary kriging and was generally comparable to IDW and RFsp, outperforming simpler deterministic approaches such as NN and TS, especially as spatial complexity increased (Fig. 2). In the real-world precipitation case study, RFSI performed among the best methods overall (Table 2). It frequently matched or exceeded regression kriging (RK), RF, and RFsp, and showed performance comparable to IDW in certain configurations, reflecting the strong role of local spatial dependence in this dataset. For the temperature case study, where environmental covariates were more informative, RFSI achieved the highest predictive accuracy among all tested approaches, including kriging-based and ML baselines. This indicates that combining nearest neighbor structure with covariates is particularly beneficial when both spatial and environmental drivers contribute to variability.

The methodology was successfully applied in the development of the high-resolution daily gridded meteorological dataset for Serbia [15]. That dataset demonstrated the practical value of RFSI for large-scale environmental data reconstruction, producing consistent daily temperature and precipitation fields at 1 km resolution over a multi-decadal period (Fig. 3).

Overall, detailed experimental comparisons, including cross-validation designs, uncertainty analysis, and sensitivity tests, are fully presented in Sekulić et al. (2020) [2], where RFSI is shown to be a competitive and often superior alternative to both classical geostatistical and ML-based interpolation methods.

Figure 2 Comparison of average mean absolute error (MAE) estimated for each of the interpolation methods, for all nugget-to-sill ratios and ranges. Coloured bars are average MAE for test locations from 100 different simulations. Error bars are standard errors computed from 100 simulations [2].

Table 2 Accuracy metrics, coefficient of determination (R^2) and root mean square error (RMSE) of all six prediction methods as assessed using nested leave-location-out cross-validation for the precipitation and temperature case study.

	Precipitation		Temperature	
Method	R^2 [%]	RMSE [mm]	R^2 [%]	RMSE [°C]
OK/STRK ¹	67.5	3.9	91.0	2.4
IDW	69.6	3.8	95.0	1.8
RF	49.4	4.9	95.7	1.6
RFsp	53.3	4.7	95.5	1.6
RFSI	69.5	3.8	96.6	1.4
RFSI ₀ ²	68.6	3.9	94.9	1.8

Figure 3 Annual LTM maps for all daily meteorological variables [15].

- 1 STRK — Spatio Temporal Regression Kriging
- 2 RFSI₀ — RFSI without environmental covariates

4 R package meteo

The `meteo` package [16] is an R implementation designed to support spatial and spatio-temporal modelling of meteorological and environmental variables, with a particular focus on spatio-temporal regression kriging [17] and RFSI [2]. The package provides a streamlined workflow for building predictive spatial models that combine classical geospatial data structures with modern ML approaches. A key implementation detail of RFSI is that it uses the R package `ranger` for efficient and scalable RF training, enabling fast model fitting even for large spatial datasets. A central design goal of `meteo` is interoperability with standard R spatial ecosystems. It integrates directly with `sf` [12] for vector data handling, `terra` [13] for raster processing and large-scale gridded operations, and `gstat` [18] for geostatistical workflows such as Kriging and semivariogram-based modelling. This allows users to easily compare RFSI against classical geostatistical methods within the same analytical pipeline.

The package includes a set of core functions that implement the full RFSI workflow:

- `rfsi` – builds the RFSI model using RF (`ranger`) with nearest observations and optional covariates
- `tune.rfsi` – performs hyperparameter tuning of the RFSI model
- `pred.rfsi` – generates spatial predictions for new locations or raster grids
- `cv.rfsi` – performs nested k-fold cross-validation for spatial validation and performance assessment

These functions are designed to work seamlessly with `sf` objects for station-based data and `terra` grids for raster prediction surfaces, enabling a consistent transition from point observations to continuous spatial fields.

The R package `meteo` is available on CRAN and is actively maintained, with full documentation and examples provided in the package vignette and manual. The development version, including additional examples and updates, is hosted on GitHub:

- CRAN: <https://cran.r-project.org/web/packages/meteo/index.html>
- GitHub: <https://github.com/AleksandarSekulic/Rmeteo>
- Examples: <https://github.com/AleksandarSekulic/Rmeteo/tree/master/demo>
- MeteoSerbia1km [15] application: <https://github.com/AleksandarSekulic/MeteoSerbia1km>

5 Conclusions and future work

Spatial interpolation methods range from classical deterministic approaches to geostatistical models such as Kriging, and more recently to ML techniques like RF and GBM. While Kriging explicitly models spatial autocorrelation, and ML methods capture nonlinear relationships using covariates, most ML approaches do not directly incorporate the structure of nearby observations, which is a key element of spatial dependence.

RFSI addresses this by explicitly adding observations from the nearest locations and their distances as predictors within an RF model. This creates a hybrid approach that combines geostatistical use of

nearby observations with the flexibility of ML. As a result, RFSI removes the need for variogram modelling, avoids strict stationarity assumptions, and can better handle nonlinear relationships as well as skewed or zero-inflated variables. Overall, it extends the spatial ML toolbox with a simple but effective way of embedding spatial dependence directly into the model.

Despite these advantages, RFSI has several limitations. Its performance depends on the choice of the number of neighbors, it can become computationally demanding for very large datasets, and it inherits typical RF limitations in extrapolation. It is also sensitive to sparse sampling designs, where nearest neighbor information may be less representative of local conditions.

Future developments could focus on extending RFSI to spatio-temporal settings [17] by including temporal neighbors, improving uncertainty quantification, and optimizing adaptive neighbor selection. Further improvements may come from GPU acceleration for large-scale applications and tighter integration with remote sensing products. These extensions would make RFSI more scalable and better suited for high-resolution environmental mapping problems.

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